

**UNIVERSITY
OF LATVIA**

Data Management plan

“Development of optoplasmonic doped whispering gallery mode resonator”

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Project Information

This Data Management Plan (DMP) covers the data that will be collected by Inga Brice (project leader) at University of Latvia while implementing project **LU-BA-PG-2024/1-0009** “Development of optoplasmonic doped whispering gallery mode resonator” on the development of an advanced coating combining doping WGM resonator for an active operation of the cavity together with functionalization with optoplasmonic particles for passive enhancement of the sensitivity will be explored to manufacture a hybrid active/passive system. The research is financed by the Project No 5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/I/CFLA/007 "Internal and External Consolidation of the University of Latvia" of the second round of the Consolidation and Governance Change Implementation Grants within Investment 5.2.1.1.i "Research, Development and Consolidation Grants" under Reform 5.2.1.r "Higher Education and Science Excellence and Governance Reform" of Reform and Investment Strand 5.2 of the Latvian Recovery and Resilience Mechanism Plan "Ensuring Change in the Governance Model of Higher Education Institutions". The project will be implemented between September 1, 2024 and August 31, 2025.

Planned research project outputs are experiment raw data, experiment metadata, analyzed data, deliverable data reports. All research data collected as part of this project is owned by the University of Latvia. The project leader of this project will take responsibility for the collection, management, and sharing of the research data.

Purpose

This DMP was created on September 23, 2024. This document will be used as a “living document”, and will change and grow as the development and implementation phases of the project progress. The aim and purpose of this DMP is to detail and guarantee the preservation of the data and documents collected during the project, as well as any results derived from it. Proper data management - recording of collected data, storage and dissemination of the results - is important to ensure data collected for this project is safely secured. This project will generate a variety of data over its one year. The DMP includes multiple ways to responsibly manage that data.

1. Description of data

1.1. Data to be produced and collected

This research project will generate data. The data, samples, and materials expected to be produced will consist of raw data files from experiments, experiment and method metadata, experimental analysis data files, microscopy images, photos and videos, written deliverable reports.

Raw data:

These files will consist of ASCII text directly collected from photo-detectors during measurements of transmission signal and calibration signal used for assessing the quality of the functionalized samples. Screenshots, photos (including microscopy images) and videos will be part of the raw data collection.

Experiment metadata:

Metadata file will describe the experiments and methods, including details like, sample coating materials, concentrations, fabrication and preparation procedures, experimental environment and parameters. Additionally, project leader will record any observations, procedures, and ideas generated during the course of the experiment. Metadata will be created as soon as the data is collected or produced, thus allowing efficient management.

Experimental analysis data files:

Experimental analysis data files will consist of spreadsheets and plots of the raw data that have been manipulated to yield meaningful and quantitative information and values for assessment of the functionalized microresonator quality. The analysis will be performed using best practice and acceptable methods for calculating quality factors and determining more suitable sample preparation procedures.

Written deliverable reports:

Deliverables will be text files containing analyzed and visualized data derived from raw data and other project activities

1.2. Data file formats and sizes

The data will be distributed in several widely used formats, including ASCII, tab-delimited formats (*.txt, *.dat, *.csv; size <5 MB) for raw data files compatible with spread sheets (OpenDocument *.ods and Microsoft Office *.xlsx), data analysis and visualization software files (QtiPlot *.qti, *.c and Origin *.opj; size <20 MB), which will be used to generate data plots (*.png for bitmap graphics and .svg for vector graphics; size <10MB). Photos (*.jpg; also screenshots *.png; size <10MB) and videos (*.mp4; size <100MB) will be RGB colored with resolution determined by the camera. Instructional material and relevant technical reports will be provided as written documents (OpenDocument files *.odt and Microsoft office *.docx; size <100MB; editable for personal use) and presentations/posters (OpenDocument files *.odp and Microsoft office *.pptx; size <100MB; editable for personal use) converted to PDF format (*.pdf; size <100MB; for sharing) for better compatibility. Publications will be prepared using LaTeX files (*.tex, *.bib, *.sty, etc.; size <10MB) together with image files (editable OpenDocument images *.odg exported as *.png, *.svg or *.pdf; size <10MB). Other file formats, depending on required analysis may be used. A total volume of 1000 files with storage demand of 5 GB is anticipated.

1.3. Data storage

All data will be stored on the project leaders *OneDrive* personal cloud storage linked with the work e-mail provided by the University of Latvia. This includes all data levels: raw data, metadata, analyzed data, and deliverable reports. Of these, the raw and analyzed data, which is equivalent to data that is published in scientific journals will be made publicly accessible using *Zenodo* repository.

2. Documentation and quality

2.1. Data organization

Electronic data will be organized in folders with appropriate identifying file names. *OneDrive* folder “Postdoc project” will contain two sub folders – “raw data” and “deliverables”. For raw data, the folder names for each data set will including the acquisition date and short descriptor. Each individual data set folder will contain data files named with a short descriptor, experiment metadata, data analysis files, screenshots, photos, plots, etc. For other deliverables, folder name will specify which deliverable is stored inside. Report document will be named using short descriptors and include version numbers. Each folder may contain sub-folders with multiple versions of the document, additional raw editable copies of images, plots and other visuals included in the report file.

See project folder organization and naming example below:

OneDrive

- Postdoc Project
 - Raw data
 - YYYYMMDD data set descriptor
 - sample1_sample_descriptor1.txt
 - sample2_sample_descriptor2.txt
 - sample3_sample_descriptor3.txt
 - experiment_metadata.txt
 - sample1_screenshot.png
 - sample1_photo.jpg
 - sample2_screenshot.png
 - sample2_photo.jpg
 - sample3_screenshot.png
 - sample3_photo.jpg
 - YYYYMMDD other data set descriptor
 - ...
 - Deliverables
 - D1 Know-how on optoplasmonic doped WGM microresonator fabrication
 - Know_how_V2.odt
 - Know_how_V1
 - Know_how_V1.odt
 - Images
 - image1_descriptor.jpg
 - image2_descriptor.jpg
 - image3_descriptor.jpg
 - graph1_descriptor.odg
 - graph1_descriptor.svg
 - graph1_descriptor.pdf
 - graph2_descriptor.odg
 - graph2_descriptor.svg
 - graph2_descriptor.png
 - D2.1 Report on the quality of surface functionalized optoplasmonic doped WGM microresonator
 - D2.2 Prototype
 - D 3.1 Data management plan
 - D 3.2 Original scientific articles

- D 3.3 Public engagement activities
- D3.4 Project proposal
- D3.5 Project final scientific report

2.2. Data quality control measures

Project will generate a large volume of data, some of which may not be appropriate for sharing since it may involve data quality issues like “missing data”, “incorrect data”, “irrelevant data” etc. Day-to-day quality assessment will be the responsibility of the Project Leader. To ensure data quality control, calibration data will be recorded, data capture protocols will be developed, and multiple samples will be fabricated for measurements. For the data set collection and analysis, quality will also be assured through discussions with project advisor. Data will be available and cited in scientific journal publication, where it will undergo peer review. All methods for analysis will be published in full detail in peer-reviewed open source publications. Researchers will be able to access published data using *Zenodo* repository. Data will be maintained to enable re-use of the data.

3. Storage and backup

Storage and backup will be ensured for the duration of the project by the project leader during the project. All data will be stored on the project leaders personal work laptop in a folder synced with *OneDrive* cloud storage linked with the work e-mail provided by the University of Latvia. *OneDrive* file storage offers high-level data preservation, security and accessibility by automatic syncing, back up, multiple version storing, and selective data sharing options. Chosen storage option will mitigate data loss and data corruption risk. Relevant data and publication drafts will be shared with co-investigators, and partners. Only authorized members and project partners will have access to the storage. All methods for analysis will be published in detail in peer-reviewed publications. To facilitate the sharing of data, published data will be made openly accessible using *Zenodo* repository. Unpublished data will be shared on request.

4. Legal and ethical requirements

All research data collected as part of this project is owned by the University of Latvia. The project leader of this project will take responsibility for the collection, management, and sharing of the research data. Online and archival sources will be cited and clearly acknowledged in the research outputs.

At this stage, the project produces no sensitive or personal data. No particular ethical issue is foreseen with the data to be used or produced by the project. If these change, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at the University of Latvia, and the DMP will be updated accordingly.

5. Accessibility and long term storage

During the project, we will be using *OneDrive* cloud storage to exchange data between partners. Research data on which the publications will be based, and other relevant milestone deliverable files of the project will be stored safely for at least ten years. Data that is outdated or temporary in nature will be deleted at the end of the project. The long-term strategy for maintaining the data generated during the project is to keep all original data on the hard drive dedicated solely to the project. The expected total size of the remaining data is about 5 GB. Should the project leader leave the employment at University of Latvia, upon their departure the head of Quantum Optics laboratory of Institute of Atom Physics of Spectroscopy, Faculty of Science and Technology, University of Latvia, would become the keeper of the data and provide it to others as appropriate.

Target audience: researchers, students, potentially also the researchers at industrial and academic research organizations working in the area of optical microresonators.

The reuse of know-how and prototype deliverables will be restricted due to the intellectual property rights and potential possibility to license them in the future. At the moment, project leader is not aware of any other restrictions on the reuse of data. If issues arise during the project, they will be discussed with legal/ethical advisors and DMP will be updated.

Data underpinning published research papers will be made publicly available in the *Zenodo* repository at the time of the article's publication. For making the envisioned publications widely accessible, open source scientific journals will be preferred. *Zenodo* repository will be used to publish other project outputs such as deliverable reports. With these sharing and storing practices in place, FAIR principles will be supported.

6. Responsibility and resources

The project leader is responsible for the secure storage and preservation of the generated digital research data. The storage costs of approximately 50 € (hard drive) will be covered by the project's budget. No additional resources are needed for data management and storage, as University of Latvia already provides their employees with and unlimited *OneDrive* cloud storage linked to their work e-mails and *Zenodo* repository is free of charge.